

ANALYSIS OF ERRORS OF OPTOELECTRONIC MOISTURE METERS

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Abstract.

The variety of existing measurement schemes puts the issue of choosing the optimal measurement scheme and optimal parameters of metrological indicators according to their structure (random and systematic errors) to the fore. It should be noted that most moisture meters are built according to the Lagorfmic scheme.

Keywords:

Lagorfmic, optoelectronic, Gradation, System, gauge, multiplicative, temperature control, temperature, information.

Introduction.

The error of optical moisture meters is determined in two stages:

- a) when choosing the optimal measurement scheme;
- b) when adjusting and checking the moisture meter;

The variety of existing measurement schemes puts the issue of choosing the optimal measurement scheme and optimal parameters of metrological indicators according to their structure (random and systematic errors) to the fore. It should be noted that most moisture meters are built according to the Lagorfmic scheme. Output in use in working state U_{out} -signals do not depend on parameters such as w -humidity in the information temperature and changes in external factors, but also on parameters that do not have an information temperature for the environment under investigation. That is, it depends on θ - temperature of the

environment, U_{sou} -source voltage, t -time, y -concentration of non-informational parameters, θ_c -temperature of the controlled environment, η -various mechanical impurities.

Therefore, the incoming signal and its transmission coefficient are functions of external factors and parameters that do not have informational characteristics.

$$U_{\text{out}} = F(U_{\text{nor}}\theta, U_{\text{sou}}t) = U_{\text{nor}}A_i; K_{pr} = \varphi(\omega, y, \eta, \theta_c), \quad (1)$$

Here, U_{nor} - is the nominal value of outgoing signals under normal conditions; A – coefficient of influence of external factors on outgoing signals; (A - determined from experiments).

When designing wet meters, in order to ensure the linearity of the scales, it is necessary to choose such measurement conditions that the transfer coefficient is linearly dependent on informational and non-informative parameters or close to it.

Experiments and results.

These conditions are met when the humidity is around 10-25%. In this case, the transfer coefficient is expressed as a linear function

$$K_{\text{np}}[1 - K_{\omega}(\omega - \omega_0)][1 - K_y(y - y_0)][1 - K_{\theta_c}(\theta_c - \theta_{c0})]\eta = [1 - K_{\omega}(\omega - \omega_{n.in})]B_i. \quad (2)$$

Under normal conditions, $u=u_0$; $c=c_0$; $\eta=1$; $B_i=1$; The conduct coefficient K_{script} $1 - K_w(w - w_{\text{min}})$, where K_w – coefficient, characterizes the change in the coefficient of conducting the controlled environment to unit w -humidity; K_y , K_{θ_c} – sizes that characterize the conduct coefficient, the y -noinformation environment, change in relation to unity concerts. This takes into account the change in temperature to 1°C .

σ_i -random mistake (normally $A_i = 1$ and $B_i = 1$) is determined by the following expression

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_{\omega i}(\omega_{\text{max}} - \omega_{\text{min}})/S_{\omega}, \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda S_w – namlik o'lchagichni sezgirligini o'rtacha qiymatga nisbatan

($S_w = dU_{\text{БЫХ}}/d_w$), bunda $\sigma_{wi}^2 = D[U_{\text{БЫХ}}]$ – chiquvchi signallarni dispersiyasi.

For a logometric structured scheme, the characterization of random errors is written with the following expression

$$\sigma_i = \delta_U = \sqrt{\frac{q_1}{z_{max}^2} + \left[\frac{\gamma}{(1-\gamma z_{max}^2)^2} + \frac{\delta_{U_0}^2}{\delta_U^2} - \left(\frac{2}{z_{max}} - \gamma \right) q_1 \right] \gamma}, \quad (3)$$

Here q_1 – R - depends on the correlation coefficient, it depends on the 1st base signal, it measures channels 2, the δ_{sh} and δ the squares of U -errors, it depends on electrical noise and photoelectronic signals.

$$q_1 = 2(-R) + \frac{\delta_{\text{ш}}^2}{\delta_U^2}, \quad (4)$$

In this case, δ_{He} is a homogeneous for relative error base and measuring channels and is not dependent on their line of change.

$$\delta_U = \frac{\sigma_1}{M[U_1]} = \frac{\sigma_2}{M[U_2]}, \quad (5)$$

Here $\sigma_1 = D[U_1]$; $\sigma_2 = D[U_2]$ – dispersion of base and measurement signals; $M[U_1]$, $M[U_2]$ – *Mathematical* expectation of U_1 base and U_2 -measurement signals; $\delta_{ht} = \sigma_s / M[U_s]$ – here σ_s , $M[U_s]$ – dispersion and mathematical expectations, It comes from noise signals; $^{\circ}K_{O.C.}$ is a relative error in replacing it with reverse; This error $^{\circ}K_{o.c} = D[K_{o.c}]$ equal; $K_{O.S.}$ is a coefficient in reverse replacement. His mathematics is not expected $-M[K_{c}]$,

$$\delta_{K_{o.c}} = \frac{\sigma_{K_{o.c}}}{M[K_{o.c}]}; \quad (6)$$

δU_{isa} relative error, $^{\circ}U_{\text{is}}$ generated from the dispersion and its $M[U_{op}]$ mathematical expectation

$$\delta_{U_{\text{оп}}} = \frac{\sigma_{U_{\text{оп}}}}{M[U_{\text{оп}}]}; \quad (7)$$

Z_{max} –parameter, u shkalalarni $w_{min} - w_{max}$ oraliqda o'zgargandagi tayanch kanalini signallarini nisbiy o'zgarishini xarakterlaydi.

$$Z_{max} = K_{\omega}(\omega_{max} - \omega_{min}); \quad (8)$$

Here K_{ω} is the relative conductivity coefficient that corresponds to the unit

measurement of the controlled object, humidity; w_{min} , w_{max} – values of humidity max and min. respectively; γ – unsavory size, coefficient that characterizes the scales of the measuring printer

$$\gamma = \frac{\omega - \omega_{min}}{\omega_{max} - \omega_{min}}, \quad (9)$$

Here w is the value of moisture being measured;

The expression of detecting random errors is derived from the following hypotheses:

(a) *Random* variation of U , $K_{O.S.}$ and U

b) they are not interconnected, they are not free from U_1 and U_2

c) their cross-correlated correlation coefficient- R

The characteristics of i -systematic errors corresponding to the w_{max} - w_{min} measurement diaphragm depend on changing external factors and are determined by the following expression

$$\Delta_i = \frac{M[U_{\text{ВЫХ}} - U_{\text{ВЫХ.НОМ}}]}{[S_{cp}(\omega_{max} - \omega_{min})]}, \quad (10)$$

Here's $M[U_{\text{Вых}} - U_{\text{Вых.ном}}]$ – It's a outgoing signal, it's a mathematical expectation of nominal terms $A_1=A_2=B_1=B_2=1$; S_{cr} is the average value of the sensitivity of the moistmeter relative to the moisture being measured;

$$S_{cp} = \frac{\Delta U_{\text{ВЫХ.НОМ}}}{\Delta \omega} = \frac{U_{\text{ВЫХmax}} - U_{\text{ВЫХmin}}}{(\omega_{max} - \omega_{min})}, \quad (11)$$

Bu erda $U_{\text{ВЫХmax}}$, $U_{\text{ВЫХmin}}$ –namlikni w_{max} -maksimal va w_{min} -minimal qiymatlariga mos, chiquvchi signallar.

Systemic errors that are characterized by external and non-informational parameters of controlled modes or materials are expressed as follows

$$\Delta_i = \left[1 - \frac{A_1 B_1}{(A_2 B_2)} \right] - \left[1 - \frac{A_1 B_1}{(A_2 B_2 b) \gamma} \right], \quad (12)$$

Here $Z_{max} = K_w (w_{max} - w_{min})$; $b = K_{O.S.} / K_{O.S.pom} - K_{O.S.}$ -sizes, which are used in the process of being, depend on the device's inverse connection coefficient and nominal reverse connection coefficient; Coefficients that affect external factors

and the measuring channel, respectively, A_1 , B_1 and A_2 , 2.

Analysis of the above expressions shows that random errors consist of multipliative excesses that depend on the addative (first add-on) and parameter γ the error.

It δ signals U_1 and U_2 - at small values of relative average square edge, the addictive mistake is also small, and their R-interconnection is greater.

$R \approx 1$ qiymatda additiv hatolik signalning shovqinga nisbati bilan aniqlanadi.

System errors include the following external factors:

environmental temperature, source voltage, working time, base and measuring channel, signal conduction coefficient, measurement diaphragm, device reverse algae coefficient, ratio of signals used.

Systematic mistakes can be reduced by thermosticization or temperature correction of the measuring chain. At the same time, it is necessary to increase the voltage and reduce the measurement diaphragm. It is also necessary to put the reverse contact coefficient in a single margin.

By applying a functional spread, you can easily eliminate recent mistakes.

Let's take a look at the main mistakes of the functional spread optoelectronic moistmeter.

The source of errors is:

- incorrect configuration of waves of light that spread under exponential law;
- incorrect accents of exponentials by the photoconferencing;
- the lack of exposure to light diodes, temperature and temporary effects by a margin.

In general, the source of the exponential impulse distribution is the generator, key, and RC-chain.

If in advance, the generator is charged with an impuls with a limited duration of insurance, then when connecting the C-capacity and the R-resistor

parallel, the resistor voltage

$$U_R = -Ee^{-t/\tau}, \quad (13)$$

Here *is the* E-impulse amplitude; τ – the constant of time; t - time;

If the light diode has a linear volt-ampere and power characteristics, we will have the following expressions when a pulse passes through it by exponential law

$$i_{cд} = I_0 e^{-t/\tau}; \quad (14)$$

$$P_{иcл} = kI_0 e^{-t/\tau}, \quad (15)$$

Here i_{sd} – light diode current; I_0 – the initial value of the current (maximum); N_{is} the power to distribute light diode light; k is the coefficient that replaces the pulse for intensive light distribution;

The resulting embryo was allowed to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it implanted.

To correct this, it is necessary to give the light diode a beginner shift. Its value can be determined by the volt-ampere characteristics of the light diode:

$$I_{cm} = \frac{U_{cm} - U_0}{R_{cm}}, \quad (16)$$

Here U_{sm} – shift voltage; P_{it} drops the power in the light diode; R_{sm} is a swing resistance.

In this case, additional power is separated from the light diode at the expense of the shifting current. It should be considered when choosing a maximum of allowed shift.

The effect of the camera on the overall failure of the wet gauge is enormous. The resulting embryo was allowed to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it implanted.

In evaluating the properties of quality impulses, the criteria for forms for different forms and durations are consistent.

The following is the relationship between the flow of outgoing lights and voltage from the camera;

$$\tau_{\phi}(du/dt) + u(t) = S_0\Phi(t), \quad (17)$$

Here τ_{ff} is the constant time of the camera.

When the environment is illuminated by $F(t)$ - impulse light, the criterion for the quality of its production is determined by the following formula

$$F = \left(\int_0^{\infty} [U(t) - S_0\Phi(t)] dt \right) / \left(S_0 \int_0^{t_{\text{имп}}} \Phi(t) dt \right), \quad (18)$$

Here $U(t)$ is a signal coming out of the camera. The instant error is determined by the following formula, taking into account the movement of the inplog signal, the camera, depending on the inertia properties

$$\Delta^2 = \left\{ \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T [u(t + t_c) - S_0\Phi(t)] dt \right\} / \left(\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T S_0\Phi^2(t) dt \right), \quad (19)$$

Photoqabul qilgichdan chiqayotgan signal aniqlaymiz.

Fotoqabul qilgichni o'tish harakteristikasi quydagi formula bilan aniqlanadi

$$S_{\text{неп}}(t) = S_0(1 - e^{-t/\tau_{\phi}}). \quad (20)$$

Fotoqabul qilgichni impuls xarakteristikasi

$$S_{\text{имп}}(t) = u(t) = (S_0/\tau_{\phi})e^{-t/\tau_{\phi}}. \quad (21)$$

Through the impulse characteristics of the photographer, we can find the outgoing signal from it, when the token is affected, change over time:

$$u(t) = \int_0^T S_{\text{имп}}(t)\Phi(t - \tau_{\phi}) d\tau \quad (22)$$

Or

$$u(t) = \int_0^T S_{\text{имп}}((t - \tau_{\phi}))\Phi(\tau) d\tau. \quad (23)$$

The law of change in flow

$$\Phi(t) = \Phi_0 e^{-t/\tau_{\text{экс}}} \quad (24)$$

Here's the exponential time constant; When squealing from a camera

$$u(t) = (\Phi_0 S_0 \alpha e^{-\alpha t} / \beta (1 - e^{-\beta t})), \quad (25)$$

$$\text{Here } \alpha = 1/\tau_{\phi} ; \beta = 1/\tau_{\text{экс}}.$$

Knowing the signals coming out of the measurement modifier, they can be

evaluated with the following criteria

$$F = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \left| \frac{\Phi_0 S_0 \alpha e^{-\alpha t}}{\beta} (1 - e^{-\beta t}) - \Phi_0 S_0 \alpha e^{-\beta t} \right| dt}{\Phi_0 S_0 \int_0^{t_u} e^{-\beta t} dt} \quad (26)$$

After the changes, we take the following

$$F = \frac{1}{(1 + \tau_{\Phi} / \tau_{\text{ЭКС}})(1 - e^{t_u / \tau_{\text{ЭКС}}})} \quad (27)$$

Analysis of results.

As you can see from this formula, the accent (prosperous) fauto correct is dependent on time cyclic and exponential light impulse radiation.

One of the disadvantages of the light diode is that it does not work by a margin of temporary and temperature, which determines the power to distinguish a wave of light through the intangible coefficient, % :

$$K_{\theta} = \Delta P \cdot 100 / (P_{\text{max}} \Delta \theta), \quad (28)$$

Here Δ , N is in the given temperature diaphragm, the intensity of the distribution of light; ROP is the maximum value of the intensity of light distribution; α is the temperature diaphragm. Δ

The following methods can be used to reduce the power of light diode to one margin of light distribution:

- термосохлаждение (термостатированием)
- insert thermosespectric elements into the chain of sources of light diode
- optimization of resistance value in the chain of sources
- Enter reverse contact and shift thermosescent parameters in the working section
- bringing the power of radiation to the marble
- introduction of tachkosing of optical channels.

Checking and grading the optical wet gauge **One** of the main stages of grading is to set samples in certain humidity.

Sample testing (Attiestication), with certain moisture measurement instruments, is carried out in the following sequence:

The humidity in the sample is taken on average, the values derived from several parallel measurements. Systematic mistakes are taken into account.

In this case, the medium arithmetic value is determined by the following formula. Water is added to the material in a sunny way:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (29)$$

Here x_i is the unit measurement;

2) The value of the humidity of the quality sample is determined as follows

$$\bar{x}^* = \bar{x} - q,$$

Here q is the correctness of systematic mistakes;

After correcting the mistake is done as follows, an example of the diomodda is taken, and its humidity is determined by certain methods for this substance. Then the average value of the humidity in it is determined by the following formula after n-parallel measurements:

$$\bar{x}_1 = (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i) / n. \quad (30)$$

Then a sunflower sample is taken from the soaked substance;

$$x_{1,2} = \bar{x}_1 + x_2, \quad (31)$$

Here x_2 is given the moisture received in the sample, equal to the following

$$x_2 = (Gx_1 + 100G_B) / (G + G_B); \quad (32)$$

G - mode mass; G_{in} is the mass of water.

The mass of water is determined, to ensure the necessary humidity, and is found in the following expression

$$G_B = G(x_{1,2} - 2x_1) / (\bar{x}_1 - x_{1,2} + 100). \quad (33)$$

And the average value of the sun's sample humidity is found in the following expression

$$\bar{x}_{1,2} = (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i) / n, \quad (34)$$

From this expression, we find the final correcting value

$$q = x_1 - \bar{x}_1. \quad (35)$$

The absolute boundary value of all sample samples is as follows

$$\Delta \bar{x}^* = \pm \sqrt{2\Delta x_2^2}, \quad (36)$$

Here Δx_2 is found in the following expression;

$$\Delta x_2 \sqrt{(\Delta G_B/G_B) + (\Delta G/G)^2}. \quad (37)$$

Conclusions.

1. The opto-electronic moisture control system of textile materials was studied and analyzed. The results show that the light-emitting power of a light-emitting diode is determined by a linear approximation of its volt-ampere characteristic.
2. An analysis of the errors of the opto-electronic moisture meter measuring textile materials was carried out. The results of the analysis show that random errors consist of additive (first additive) and multiplicative terms depending on the error parameter g . In addition, its errors depend on the optimal selection of the measurement scheme and the accuracy of the humidity gradation. Sources of errors, i.e., their causes, are shown.

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